

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TEACHERS' MEDIATION AND AUTONOMY

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ABSTRACT

The present study was designed to investigate the role of teacher as a mediator and its relationship with teacher autonomy in Iranian EFL context. To achieve this goal, a sample of 60 EFL teachers who were teaching English in different levels of language institutes was selected. The participants' views towards the importance of the twelve features of mediation were asked by means of Waren (1995) mediation questionnaire. Teachers' Autonomy Scale (Pearson & Hall, 1993) was also used to reflect the elements of teacher autonomy construct. The descriptive statistics revealed that Iranian EFL teachers seldom use mediation features in the classroom but they considered them as important techniques in the classroom. The results of Pearson correlation indicated a positive and significant relationship between teacher's mediation and teacher autonomy. The findings of this study are informative enough to arouse the interest of the relevant authorities to consider the potentiality of mediation techniques and take the necessary steps to improve teaching quality.

KEYWORDS: Teachers' mediation – teachers' autonomy

INTRODUCTION

Mediation holds that people around learners act as mediators who “may be the parent, facilitator, teacher, or some significant other who plays the intentional role of explaining, emphasizing, interpreting, or extending the environment so that the learner builds up a meaningful internal model of the context or the world experienced” (Seng, Pou, & Tan, 2003, p. 11). When this takes place in language classrooms, teachers should interact with students and help them to apply the language themselves instead of only providing them with the language knowledge (Fisher, 2005). With the emphasis on facilitating learner autonomy and life-long education in recent reform efforts, it has become significant that students are supposed to self-control their learning and become more active thinkers and problem-solvers (Yang, 2003).

The construct of mediation is central to the sociocultural theory of Vygotsky (1981, 1986; Lantolf, 2000) because it provides a means of studying social processes involved in situated

language learning and use (Appel & Lantolf, 1994; Hall, 1995). Reflecting Vygotsky's notion that learning originates in the social mediation provided by interactions, such research in second language acquisition (SLA) questions the metaphors of input and output (e.g., Swain, 2000; van Lier, 2000). Mediation is also central to the study of collaborative interactions. Vygotsky (1981) argues that human activities and mental functioning are mediated and facilitated by tools, cultural practices, and artifacts, the most extensive tool being language.

By assuming the role of mediator, teachers can empower their learners by helping them acquire the needed knowledge, skills, and strategies in order to become effective and independent. Therefore, familiarity with these mediation features is helpful for EFL teachers to help their students with their learning and equip them with the necessary abilities to cope with challenges in the future. Williams and Burden (1997) indicate that teachers' perceptions about mediation are likely to affect how they approach teaching and help their students to become autonomous learners.

The term autonomy refers to one's ability to decide the laws for oneself. The concept is found in moral, political and bio-ethical philosophy. It has been defined in a number of ways. Holec (1981, p. 3) defines it as "the ability to take charge of one's learning" by determining the objectives; defining the contents and progressions; selecting methods and techniques to be used; monitoring the procedure of acquisition by properly speaking; and evaluating what has been acquired. Autonomy is an approach to learning and the main characteristic of autonomy as an approach to learning is that students take some significant responsibility for their own learning over and above responding to instruction (Boud, 1988).

In autonomous learning, the exact nature of teachers' role like that of learners varies according to contexts and personalities involved. Generally, a teacher in such learning is a facilitator, an organizer, a resource person providing learners with feedback and encouragement, and a creator of learning atmosphere and space. In other words, a teacher works as a guide, a cooperative and an initiator rather than an authority. For Camilleri (1999), "the most important role includes 'awareness' of self. Furthermore, the teacher of autonomous learner(s) is aware of her own personal influence on the learning process, understands pedagogy, and is skilled in management" (p. 36).

Previous research indicated that most language teachers had little knowledge of mediation, which affected their implementation of mediation in the classroom (e.g., Grosser & Waal, 2008; Guo, 2004; Sun, 2007). Yang (2006) reports in his research that "as for teachers' mediative classroom behaviors, teachers' self-assessment is overtly above students' evaluation to them" (p. 83). Students anticipate that EFL teachers can help them develop self-confidence to learn English well, teach them effective learning strategies, set their own learning goal, and facilitate their social enhancement (Lai, 2004). Students are inclined to learn autonomously with the help of teachers' mediation in the classroom (Guo, 2004).

This study tried to focus on whether teachers act as mediators in Iranian EFL context. In this way, the purpose of this research was to examine the relationship between teacher's mediation

and the factors affecting teacher perceptions of their autonomy. Therefore, the following research questions were posed to address the purpose of the study:

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Do Iranian EFL teachers consider mediation techniques as important in class?

To what extent do Iranian EFL teachers play the role of mediators?

Is there any relationship between teachers' attitudes towards mediation and their autonomy?

METHODOLOGY

Participants

The selection of the participants of this study was carried out based on convenient sampling procedure since the lack of access to EFL teachers imposed limitations on selecting the participants randomly. The participants of the present study were 60 male and female Iranian EFL teachers between the ages of 23 to 35. These participants were a group of EFL teachers who have been teaching in intermediate and advanced levels in Jahad Language School, English College, and Iran Language Institute in Kermanshah.

Instruments

To evaluate teachers' mediation ability, the Warren (1995) *Teacher Mediation Questionnaire* was employed. This questionnaire consists of three parts. The first part is designed to seek personal information from participants, about their age, teaching experience, and gender. They were asked to provide their names if they would like to be interviewed, otherwise they were coded as anonymous. The second part is composed of 12 statements, and each statement examines the participants' views of the importance of the twelve features of mediation. The participants were asked to rate how important they think each statement is on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from "Very important" to "Not important at all". The third part contains the same 12 statements but requests the participants to indicate how often they try to carry out each of these features on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from "Very often" to "Never".

To measure teacher autonomy, the *Teacher Autonomy Scale* (TAS) Questionnaire administered by Pearson and Hall (1993) was applied. This questionnaire (TAS) is comprised of 31 questions divided into two parts. The TAS is comprised of 31 questions divided into two parts: (a) 18 questions dealing with teaching information (teacher autonomy) and (b) 13 questions dealing with teaching conditions. As part of this construct validation, the author attempted to establish the related constructs underlying each of the 18 questions that comprise the construct of teacher autonomy (see Appendix B).

This questionnaire was designed primarily by Charter (1974) and the reliability of the subscales and total instruments were examined using Cronbach Alpha. The result of Cronbach of reliability calculation equaled to 0.80, which is acceptable and could be considered further studies.

Procedure

In order to conduct the study and collect the required data related to the research questions and hypotheses, the following procedure was followed. The copies of the questionnaires were distributed among the participants of study. In this research, two questionnaires were given to EFL teachers who were involved in teaching in Jihad Language School, Language College, and Iran Language Institute in Kermanshah. The questionnaires were designed in English.

Before administering the questionnaires, a complete explanation was given about the aim of the research, the questionnaires and how they should be answered. EFL teachers were assured that the results would be used for this research and their views would be kept completely confidential. The questionnaires sheets were filled by sixty teachers with more than one year of teaching experience. At first the participants were asked to complete the Mediation Questionnaire for Language Teachers and the questionnaires of teacher autonomy scale (TAS) while completing the questionnaire through explanation was provided to each teacher by the researcher. Then the relationship between teachers' mediation, autonomy, experience and actual practice was examined.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The participants' performance on the second part of the questionnaire concerning the teachers' attitudes towards the significance of mediation techniques in their teaching practice is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of participants' performance on the second part of mediation questionnaire

Items	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
m1	60	4.00	5.00	4.8833	.32373
m2	60	2.00	5.00	4.2333	.81025
m3	60	3.00	5.00	4.3667	.68807
m4	60	3.00	5.00	4.7000	.53043
m5	60	3.00	5.00	4.3500	.63313
m6	60	2.00	5.00	4.1500	.79883
m7	60	2.00	5.00	3.9333	.79972
m8	60	2.00	5.00	4.0333	.78041
m9	60	2.00	5.00	4.0500	.76856
m10	60	1.00	5.00	4.1667	.92364
m11	60	2.00	5.00	3.9000	.85767
m12	60	1.00	5.00	4.1500	.87962

As the above table shows, the mean of the teachers' responses to the most of the 12 items is 4. Converting to Likert scale, it means that teachers considered these items as *quite important*. The frequency and percentage of teachers' attitudes are provided in Table 2.

Table 2: The frequency and percentage of teachers' attitudes towards the significance of mediation

	Frequency	Percent
Not Important at all	.25	.41
Not very Important	1	1.8
Neutral	8	13.36
Quite Important	26.83	43.73
Very Important	23.92	40.7
Total	60	100.0

The results indicated that almost 44 percent of the teachers believed that mediation techniques are quite important. Furthermore, about 41 percent of EFL teachers regarded mediation as a very important technique in the classroom and therefore, the first research question of the study was verified.

The descriptive statistics such as frequency, mean and standard deviation were used in order to investigate the second research hypothesis of this study in finding whether Iranian EFL teachers play the role of mediator or not. The same statistics were calculated for the third part of the questionnaire concerning the teachers' actual practice in their current classroom and the results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of participants' performance on the third part of mediation questionnaire

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
m13	60	1.00	5.00	1.8167	.91117
m14	60	1.00	5.00	1.9000	.93337
m15	60	1.00	4.00	1.5500	.64899
m16	60	1.00	4.00	1.4667	.62346
m17	60	1.00	4.00	1.8000	.87914
m18	60	1.00	3.00	1.3000	.49745
m19	60	1.00	3.00	1.2000	.44341
m20	60	1.00	5.00	1.6833	.83345
m21	60	1.00	4.00	1.4167	.64550
m22	60	1.00	5.00	1.4000	.69380
m23	60	1.00	4.00	1.7667	.59280
m24	60	1.00	5.00	1.4167	.76561

Regarding the above table, the mean of the teachers' responses to almost the most of the 12 items is around 1. According to the Likert scale of the third part, it means that teachers *never* used the techniques of mediation in their classroom. The frequency and percentage of teachers' attitudes are provided in Table 4.

Table 4: The frequency and percentage of teachers' attitudes towards their actual practice in their classroom

	Frequency	Percent
Never	32.83	54.72
Hardly Ever	23.16	38.79
Sometimes	2.16	3.60
Quite Often	1.25	2.09
Very Often	.6	.8
Total	60	100.0

The results indicated that nearly 55 percent of the teachers stated that they never used the techniques of mediation in their teaching practice. In addition, about 39 percent of EFL teachers hardly ever used mediation technique in the classroom. Therefore, Iranian EFL teachers never play the role of mediator in the classroom, and the second research question of the study was verified.

In order to investigate the third research hypothesis in finding whether there is any relationship between teacher's mediation and their autonomy, a Pearson correlation was performed. The results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Pearson correlation between teacher's mediation and their autonomy

		Autonomy	Mediation
Autonomy	Pearson Correlation	1	.778**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	60	60
Mediation	Pearson Correlation	.778**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	60	60

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results, as shown in Table 5, indicated that there is a high, moderate and significant relationship between the teacher's mediation and their autonomy ($r = .77, p < .05$). In other words, the more Iranian EFL teachers were autonomous, the more they knew the importance of mediation in the classroom. Thus, the third research question of the study was verified.

The descriptive statistics revealed that Iranian EFL teachers often did not use mediation features in the classroom and they did not have adequate knowledge of mediation. Most of the participating teachers regarded the role of mediator as the person that clarifies the instruction, provides justification for activities, explains how to do activities, develops learners' self-confidence, teaches effective learning strategies, helps learners to set challenges for themselves, monitors changes for themselves and solves the problems, teaches students to work co-operatively, helps learners to develop as individuals, fosters the learners' sense of belonging.

The participants of the study did not use the mediation techniques in their classroom. The results of Pearson correlation indicated a positive and significant relationship between teacher's mediation and teacher autonomy.

The findings of the present study were in line with a number of previous relevant studies such as Tang (2009), Peng (2005) and Fu, (2003) who found that most EFL teachers in China have no knowledge of mediation and thus are unable to mediate students' learning. Similar to the findings of the studies like Grosser and Waal (2008), Sun (2007) and Xu (2006) who indicated that most EFL teachers have little or no exposure to knowledge of the role of mediation, the results of this study showed that Iranian EFL teachers do not have adequate knowledge of the role of mediation. The results of this study can support those of Mueller (1986) and Oskamp (1991) who found teachers' knowledge of mediation which influenced their behaviors differently since cognition was one of the fundamentals of their implementation of the mediator role.

This study shed lights to the dynamic relationship between teachers' mediation and development of their autonomy in the context of the classroom. Although there is a dearth of research exploring relationship between teachers' mediation and autonomy, these findings partially appear to be consistent with those of Collins (1996) and Gilroy (1993) who found that teaching transmitting information as well as preparing students to acquire knowledge on their own is relied on the autonomous teachers. Similarly, Draves (1980) found that only if teachers become self-regulated learners can teacher autonomy and accountability be practiced because one can hardly be autonomous or accountable for one's own learning if the process is planned and organized by others.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of statistical analyses, one conclusion that can be drawn is that most Iranian EFL teachers did not have the knowledge of mediation, resulting in not performing the role of mediator in the classroom. EFL teachers tended to agree on the point that mediation have significant capability in engaging learners in actual practice of language learning. In this regard, the significant evidence was provided to confirm that the use of mediation techniques in classroom context can provide clear and appropriate purposes for learning contents, reflect real world practice, require learners to use target language for a communicative purpose, provide opportunities for learners to negotiate meaning, use and expand their existing language resources and notice how language is used and finally involve learners in a mode of thinking and doing.

From theoretical point of view, the present study added the potential influence of the mediation in promoting learners' control of their own behavior, goal-setting, sharing and individuality, sense of belonging and belief in positive outcomes.

Moreover, the use of mediation in classroom can fully engage EFL learners in learning activities and provide conditions for learners to take more advantages of classroom time by involving in tasks. From pedagogical point of view, the present study provided precious implications for EFL syllabus designers as it was implicitly identified some disconcerting problems with the current ELT textbooks. The results implied that this textbook needs some revisions in terms of the activities. It seems that overemphasize on providing rich reading comprehension texts made the authors neglected the potential role of activities in consolidating the learning process.

The implementation of this study in its present suggested form can be justified in terms of some limitations. The participants were selected according to available sampling. The study can be duplicated using procedures that allow a higher degree of randomization and eventually more generalizability.

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